

Metadata-driven design of graphical user interface components for data entry and validation

Version 0.7 from 12.08.2015

¹ DKFZ Partnerstandort Frankfurt/Mainz – Mitglied im Deutschen Konsortium für Translationale Krebsforschung

1. Introduction and Objectives

There are multiple database management systems, database tools and data structures in clinical and research information systems. Consequently, there is semantically and syntactically heterogeneous information in each organization [1]. The origin of the heterogeneity can be found between different data sources, in the attribute naming, encodings, content, precision granularity, modelling, language and quantity of data stored [2]. The implementation of a metadata repository supports the harmonization of data and the mapping of metadata and data [3].

The project described herein aims at easing the creation and usage of clinical forms, based on a metadata repository. The developed software libraries enable the automatic rendering of labels, tooltips, input widgets and input data validation. It includes easy-to-set reusable components that software developers can effortlessly use to render clinical forms, relying on already defined metadata rather than re-inventing data elements and widgets.

Following the description of the materials and methods used and the presentation of the results, new software concepts were introduced to enable the creation, edition, dissemination and reusability of forms without code. Using the software libraries and components described in this document, it is demonstrated how an enhanced software solution can enable non-computer-science-specialists to build and reuse clinical forms through a web interface and still keeping data well documented and harmonised in diverse systems and databases.

2. Material and Methods

For correct validation, as well as interpretation, there is usually more information needed than just the name and value of an attribute. This can include for example a detailed prose description or definition, the expected data type and a list of valid values. This kind of additional data is commonly known by the term metadata and can simply be understood as “data about data” [4].

Metadata can be further distinguished by being content related or not [4]. An example for non-content-oriented metadata is some sort of non-descriptive ID number, e.g., the social security number of a person, which does not say anything about the person itself, but allows identifying an information object. Content-oriented metadata instead enables to make assumptions about its content, e.g., the weight and height of a person.

The range of metadata depends on the specialty of some use case, for example, describing books in a library will include the title and the author. With that said it has to be agreed upon the used metadata in advance. In the use case at hand, the attributes used in a dataset shall be annotated with metadata. This is quite common in dealing with the storage of data which has resulted in developing a relevant standard, ISO/IEC 11179, Information Technology -- Metadata registries (MDR) [5].

ISO 11179 is comprised of six parts where the focus will be on part three “Registry metamodel and basic attributes” [6], which describes what kind of metadata is needed and especially the structure of metadata registries. It allows storing metadata and enables consumers to retrieve it. All kinds of data can be defined formally by annotating appropriate metadata and these formal definitions can in turn be made broadly available in a central MDR. Such a definition of an atomic piece of data, which basically stands for any entity or fact of the real world, e.g. the blood pressure of a patient, is called a data element [7].

Java was chosen as the programming language for the project due to the cross-platform capabilities, object-orientation, use simplicity, scalability, integrated development environment (IDE) integration, large set of API available and security features. JavaServer Faces (JSF), a specification for building component-based web user interfaces is a good example of Java extensibility. JSF enables reusability of web interface components and relieves the user interface building process.

Along with JSF, standard web technologies such as HTML, CSS, Javascript, Bootstrap and jQuery were used in the user interface solution. A web-based interface runs on browsers, thus there is no need to install software on the user computer, the data is centralised, updates are easier and faster to implement and the solution is available everywhere where there is an Internet connection.

There is a central MDR where all the information about data elements can be retrieved and edited. The interfaces between the different components are implemented using the Representational State Transfer (REST) paradigm. It generalizes the concepts and methods of the World Wide Web to reuse them for the realization of any kind of distributed information system. REST relies on a lightweight representation, producing human readable results and it is easy to build. It also minimizes the coupling between the metadata repository and the user interface components [8], which means that the metadata repository can be then updated without interfering with the user interface components and vice-versa.

3. Results

First, a Java library has been created to query for data elements naming, definition and validation information. The MDRClient [9], as it is called, can be reused in Java projects to get sets of data that describe and give information about other data (i.e. metadata), from the MDR, through REST calls. This connector is useful as a separate library when there is the need to obtain metadata from the repository on a system that does not include the JavaServer Faces specification. For instance, a system that would run as a desktop application could already reuse this library to retrieve metadata. There is no need to redefine and re-implement these features on every metadata based project.

Then, a Java library that includes JSF components has been developed to ease the process of creating clinical forms by reusing rich user interface components. This library, called MDRFaces [10], runs just like other JavaServer Faces component library [11], such as Primefaces, RichFaces or ICEfaces, providing a collection of mostly visual components (widgets). In this case, the widgets are based on clinical data. After the library is added to a JSF project, these widgets are ready to be used by simply adding the desired tags to the XHTML page. For each data element included in a form, its respective widget is automatically rendered. The structure and behaviour of the system is illustrated in Figure 1 - Architecture.

Figure 1 - Architecture

Each data element defined in the metadata repository has a unique identifier, which is included in the tag definition to specify the desired visual component - the MDRFaces library automatically renders the appropriate widget for the label and necessary input widget(s). A simple code example is illustrated in Figure 2 - MDRFaces project configuration and the resulting form is represented in Figure 3 - MDRFaces form widgets example. The input types can range from a text box and a data selector to a complex pre-defined selection of values that can trigger other inputs.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml" xmlns:h="http://java.sun.com/jsf/html" xmlns:f="http://java.sun.com/jsf/core"
xmlns:ui="http://java.sun.com/jsf/facelets" xmlns:mf="http://java.sun.com/jsf/composite/mdrfaces">
<f:view locale="de">
<h:head>
<link type="text/css" rel="stylesheet" href="styles.css" />
<title>MDRFaces Example</title>
</h:head>
<h:body class="container">
<h1 class="page-header">A basic form example</h1>
<h:form styleClass="col-md-7">
<mf:formMdrField mdrId="urn:adt:dataelement:13:1" required="true"
requiredMessage="Bitte geben Sie die Patienten PLZ an." />
<br />
<mf:formMdrField mdrId="urn:mdr10:dataelement:59:1" />
<br />
<mf:formMdrField mdrId="urn:mdr10:dataelement:14:1" />
<br />
<mf:formMdrField mdrId="urn:mdr10:dataelement:3:1" />
<br />
<mf:formMdrField mdrId="urn:mdr10:dataelement:9:1" />
<br />
<div class="row">
<div class="col-md-5">
<mf:mdrLabel mdrId="urn:osse-ror:dataelement:29:1" />
</div>
<div class="col-md-7">
<mf:mdrInput mdrId="urn:osse-ror:dataelement:29:1" value="true" />
</div>
</div>
<br />
<h:commandButton value="Search" styleClass="btn btn-primary" />
</h:form>
</h:body>
</f:view>
</html>
```

Figure 2 - MDRFaces project configuration

A basic form example

Patienten PLZ

Bitte geben Sie die Patienten PLZ an.

Datum der diagnostischen Sicherung von Fernmetastasen

May 2015						
Su	Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa
26	27	28	29	30	1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30
31	1	2	3	4	5	6

Datenlieferant - Universitätsklinikum

Figure 3 - MDRFaces form widgets example

The data structure is defined remotely in a metadata repository from which the component library, reusing the MDRClient, automatically gets the necessary data to resolve the appropriate widget. As a result, JSF rich clinical forms can be quickly built and the developer does not have to fiddle with the clinical data structure definition, complexity, validation and usability issues. Domain experts are able to focus on the data structure defined in a metadata repository and developers reuse this knowledge simply through the identification of the desired data elements.

The MDRClient supports caching, which enables faster data access. It queries the metadata repository on the fly, but avoids unnecessary calls. Caching is particularly relevant when the JSF component library queries for metadata to resolve the appropriate widget and to validate the inputs of a form with a considerable number of data elements, as the number of REST calls are drastically reduced. Besides, with caching the metadata is still accessible locally even if when metadata repository becomes unreachable.

Both the connector module and the JSF components library are multilingual, providing complete widgets to be rendered in a selected language, considering labels, tooltips, data options and validations. Choosing another language has an immediate automatic effect on the form and it is also supported by the caching mechanism, as multiple languages can be cached for the same data element. Furthermore, form inputs are frequently grouped in sections according to its semantic relationship in the context of each project. The developed modules embrace this feature by being able to query the metadata repository's groups and subgroups of data elements.

MDRFaces supports automatic validation on all forms that use the library. On form submission (e.g. pressing the save button), the data widget inputs are automatically analysed and the adequate validators are executed. There are validators for date, time, float, integer and regular expressions (text fields). Date and times can be conjugated together and may be represented in different formats. Floats and integers can be also defined within a range. The validation metadata can be entered in the MDR. In case the data entered is not conformant with the data type and metadata description of the input, the form submission process is interrupted and an error description is displayed immediately underneath the input of all erroneous fields. Figure 3 - MDRFaces form widgets example depicts distinct widgets, an input in which the user is required to enter a valid value and user input focus on a date picker.

Enabling non-computer-science-specialists to create clinical forms, i.e. without requiring code development, became a priority. A form editor has been created, where users can create and edit forms based on pre-defined data element catalogues (Figure 4 - Form editor - user form list). A demonstration is available at <https://forms.demo.osse-register.de/>.

Figure 4 - Form editor - user form list

Through a web user interface and the metadata repository connector a searchable list of the available data elements is presented. The data elements are organised in groups, exactly how it is defined in the MDR. Data elements can be dragged from this list to the form, into the desired position and can then be reordered. The JSF component library enables the immediate visualisation of the widget – reusing the MDRFaces library - and available options (Figure 5 - Creating a form on the form editor). Multiple data elements, in a form of label and input field, as well as basic HTML features such as formatting, fonts, horizontal rules, links and images can be added to a form. The end user is therefore able to create complex versioned clinical forms through the selection of data items in a web user interface.

Figure 5 - Creating a form on the form editor

The form editor is also a central form repository, where the forms are stored, edited and disseminated. Its REST interface [12], supporting both JSON and XML, enables the use of the forms on other systems. Clinical registry tools can access the form detailed data and easily render them on its own JSF web application using MDRFaces. Both the user and the REST interface are secured with a central OAuth [13] authorisation and authentication system.

In order to save the input values of a form, the import utility renders specific code – standard XHTML tags – for the registry system, indicating what bean [14] methods should be executed to process the data on form submit. The ultimate goal is to enable the creation, edition, dissemination and reusability of clinical forms and also to manage input data automatically – without requiring code development. Such an integrated project has already been developed in the scope of the OSSE registry framework [15], whose components, including the MDRClient and MDRFaces, have been released as open source projects [16]. The form created in the form editor, showed in “Figure 5 - Creating a form on the form editor” was imported into a demonstration OSSE registry, as depicted in “Figure 6 - Form created in the form editor and imported into the demonstration OSSE registry”.

The screenshot shows a web application interface for the OSSE registry. At the top, there is a header with the OSSE logo, 'List of Patients (18)', and a user profile for 'Marita Muscholl'. Below the header, a patient record for 'Karl Valentin (001L60FU)' is displayed, with a birth date of '13.12.2008'. A section for 'Episodes (3)' includes buttons for '+ NEW EPISODE', 'EDIT CURRENT EPISODE', 'DELETE CURRENT EPISODE', and 'IMPORT DATA FROM LAST EPISODE'. A date range is shown from '02/02/2015' to '01/05/2015'. A modal window titled 'Episode: 25/03/2015' is open, showing a form for 'Welche Syndrome liegen vor?' (Which syndromes are present?). The form includes a 'Syndrom-Verdacht' (Syndrome Suspicion) section with 'Renale Symptome' (Renal Symptoms) and 'Maßnahmen' (Measures) listed as 'reported'. The main form area contains a question 'Besteht eine isolierte Nephronophthie ohne extrarenale Symptome?' (Is there an isolated nephronophthia without extrarenal symptoms?) and a checkbox for 'Senior-Löken-Syndrom'. Below this, there is a section for 'Symptome zum Senior-Löken-Syndrom:' (Symptoms for Senior-Löken Syndrome) with checkboxes for 'Kongenitale Leber-Amaurose', 'Erblindung im Jugend-/Erwachsenenalter', 'Retinitis pigmentosa', and 'Gesichtsfeld einschränkung'. At the bottom of the modal, there are 'Save changes' and 'Cancel' buttons.

Figure 6 - Form created in the form editor and imported into the demonstration OSSE registry

4. Discussion

MDRFaces JSF components enable the quick development of elaborate clinical forms and an abstraction from the complexity of widget design and input validation associated to a rich data structure. Unlike other tools that help creating forms, this library connects to a metadata repository specialised in clinical data. By simply setting the desired data elements retrieved from a metadata repository, a developer can build a form that automatically renders the adequate sections, labels, input widgets and automatically validates the input data according to each data element type.

The presented libraries ease the design of data entry forms, empowering the developers to easily develop clinical forms and to focus instead on the content and usability of the forms. As the system is modular and integrated in a loosely coupled manner, the data structure – Metadata Repository - can be continuously developed by clinical domain specialists, who can focus on data quality. The widget's correct rendering is ensured by MDRFaces.

The form editor, including the repository of forms, enables reusability of both forms and data entities. This assures data harmonisation throughout all registries that rely on forms built with this tool. The easy-to-use user interface and the integration with the metadata repository make it possible to effortlessly create, edit and use complex clinical forms without computer software development knowledge. Existing registries can be integrated with the form repository through REST. An integrated registry is already distributed under the OSSE registry framework. The potential of the complete project will also increase with the possibility to share, export and import generated forms into other tools, using standard of data models such as the Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium's (CDISC [17]) Operational Data Model (ODM [18]).

The project described in this document has a wider scope than a metadata driven user interface in which the metadata describes exclusively the user interface layout [19] [20]. Instead, we have a model-independent repository of data elements and a code free approach to build user interfaces (the form editor with its own form repository), with input automatic validation, based on the data elements description and form layout preferences. Unlike a description of a user interface only, our approach enables saving data in a structured

database, keeping track of what the form inputs actually represent (not only what the label declares) and harmonisation of data in multiple databases. Metadata-driven user interfaces as described in [1] aim only at form formatting, while we aim at clinical data harmonisation across different registries, code free creation of complex clinical forms and registries and at improving research.

There is another approach in the field of medical informatics to generate user interfaces from metadata - openEHR, but it is based on a different standard. openEHR is an open standard specification in health informatics that describes the management and storage, retrieval and exchange of health data in electronic health records [21] [22]. However, our focus on the caDSR, the MDR of the National Cancer Institute, previous positive experience with ISO 11179 and its broad usage lead us to use ISO 11179. This allows searching in multiple MDRs using only one interface and it is not as complex as openEHR, whose highly structured modelling approach would have resulted in a more complicated and time consuming data element definition.

Throughout the development of the MDRClient, MDRFaces and the Form Editor there were questions arising about the completeness of the data element widget options on the one hand and, on the other hand, the usability issues involved in presenting too many choices. For example, considering an MDR data element that represents a scale: should a widget with a spinner be rendered? Should it be rendered as a horizontal sequence of a predefined number of radio buttons instead? Would it be defined in the MDR or would it be a form editor local rendering option? In case it would be an option, how many options should be presented? The problematic of data elements visual representation is a topic that can easily generate discussion and thus, there was a notable amount of time dedicated to reach a good balance between covered features and offering a good user experience. This is a topic at which we continue to work on.

5. References

1. Afsarmanesh H, Ermilova E, Msanjila SS, Camarinha-Matos LM: **Modeling and Management of Information Supporting Functional Dimension of Collaborative Networks**. *Transactions on Large-Scale Data- and Knowledge-Centered Systems I*, **5740 2009**.
2. Eder J, Dabringer C, Schicho M, Stark K: **Information Systems for Federated Biobanks**. In *Transactions on Large-Scale Data- and Knowledge-Centered Systems I. Volume 5740*. Edited by Hameurlain A, Küng J, Wagner R. Springer Berlin Heidelberg; 2009:156–190. [*Lecture Notes in Computer Science*]
3. Stausberg J, Löbe M, Verplancke P, Drepper J, Herre H, Löffler M: **Foundations of a Metadata Repository for Databases of Registers and Trials**. .
4. Kashyap V, Bussler C, Moran M: *The Semantic Web: Semantics for Data and Services on the Web*. Springer; 2008.
5. **ISO/IEC 11179 Information Technology - Metadata registries** [<http://metadata-standards.org/11179/>]
6. **ISO/IEC 11179, Information technology — Metadata registries (MDR) — Part 3: Registry metamodel and basic attributes**. 2013.
7. **ISO/IEC 11179, Information technology — Metadata registries (MDR) — Part 1: Framework**. 2004.
8. Richardson L, Ruby S: *Restful Web Services*. 1st edition. Sebastopol, CA: O'Reilly; 2007.
9. **MDRClient open source code release repository**
[https://bitbucket.org/medinfo_mainz/samply.common.mdrclient]

10. **MDRFaces open source code release repository**

[https://bitbucket.org/medinfo_mainz/samply.common.mdrfaces]

11. Burns E: **True Abstraction: Composite UI Components in JSF 2.0**. 2008.

12. **OSSE Form Editor REST API Specification** [<https://forms.osse-register.de/FormEditorRESTAPISpecification.html>]

13. Hardt E: **The OAuth 2.0 Authorization Framework**. 2012.

14. **JavaBeans Spec** [<http://www.oracle.com/technetwork/java/javase/documentation/spec-136004.html>]

15. Muscholl M, Lablans M, Wagner TO, Ückert F: **OSSE – Open Source Registry Software Solution**. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases* 2014, **9**(Suppl 1):O9.

16. **OSSE for Software Developers - Getting Started**

[https://bitbucket.org/medinfo_mainz/samply.edc.osse/wiki/Home]

17. **Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium** [www.cdisc.org]

18. Breil B, Kenneweg J, Fritz F, Bruland P, Doods D, Trinczek B, Dugas M: **Multilingual Medical Data Models in ODM Format: A Novel Form-based Approach to Semantic Interoperability between Routine Healthcare and Clinical Research**. *Applied Clinical Informatics* :276–289.

19. Dengler PM, Krishnan AK, Singh J, Sanchez LM, Shankar S, Chittamuru SK, Pekic Z, Mondal N, Kumar N, Dalfo RR i: **Metadata driven user interface**. 2012.

20. deVadoss J: **Metadata-Driven User Interfaces**. 2005.

21. **What is openEHR?** [http://www.openehr.org/what_is_openehr]

22. **User Interface and openEHR data**

[<https://openehr.atlassian.net/wiki/display/dev/User+Interface+and+openEHR+data>]